

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN SOLVING ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS.

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of information and communication technologies in solving ecological problems, the processes of teaching the population how to solve ecological problems as an educational tool, at a time when modern information technologies are developed.

Keywords: economy, digital, Smart city, smart government,

Nowadays, the role of digital technologies in the modern economy has become clear and obvious. Information and communication technologies are widely used in the state, banking, industry, medicine, security and other spheres. This indicates the full and consistent introduction of modern information and communication technologies in all spheres and areas of our society. At the same time, a number of works are being carried out in our country to introduce modern technology. The resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers adopted the concept of "Smart City", according to which the main directions for the implementation of a number of projects such as "smart education", "smart transport", "smart government" were determined. This indicates that the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in our society and their practical application create an opportunity for the widespread introduction of digital technologies in all spheres.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized that "If we do not transition to a digital economy, we will be left behind. We need to develop a National Concept of the Digital Economy, which envisages the renewal of all sectors of the economy based on digital technologies. On this basis, we need to implement the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" program 1/2022, January-February (№ 00057) "Economics and Innovative Technologies" scientific electronic journal 339 <http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz> [1]." This draft resolution presents studies on the access of the population of Uzbekistan to the World Wide Web. In particular, this year it is planned to create at least 800 thousand broadband Internet ports and lay 12 thousand kilometers of fiber-optic communication lines. About 340 thousand subscribers have acquired telecommunications equipment to expand broadband networks on the Internet. Telecommunications devices distributed by region were installed by specialists.

To date, 281 thousand port devices have been installed. In accordance with the tasks set out in the State Program for the implementation of the strategy of actions in five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 - the "Year of Development of Science, Education and the Digital Economy", the President's Resolution of April 28, 2020 "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and e-government" was adopted.

The "Environmental Education and Training" module is conducted in the form of lectures and practical (seminar) sessions. The module involves the use of modern teaching methods and information and communication technologies: - in lecture classes, presentation

and electronic-didactic technologies using modern computer technologies; - in practical classes, technical means, test surveys, brainstorming, group thinking, colloquiums and other interactive teaching methods are used.

The content of the “Environmental Education and Training” module is inextricably linked with the “Landscape, Construction and Industrial Ecology”, “Environmental Protection and Sustainable Development”, “Preservation and Restoration of Bioresources” training modules in the curriculum, and serves to increase the level of professional pedagogical training of teachers in the field of environmental education and training, the use of innovative technologies and ecological innovations in the educational process. The role of the module in higher education By mastering the module, students will gain professional competence in the use and practical application of environmental innovations and information and communication technology systems in the field of environmental education and upbringing in the educational process.

List of useful literature:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni “Raqamli O‘zbekiston-2030” strategiyasini tasdiqlash va uni samarali amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida” 5 oktabr 2020 yil, PQ-6079
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining qarori, 28.04.2020 yildagi PQ-4699-sonli
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining qarori, 15.07.2019 yildagi 589- sonli
4. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining qarori, 2020-yil 17-martdagi PQ-4642- sonli
5. Леонов, С. А. (2018). Интеграция здравоохранения, образования и информационно-коммуникационных технологий в рамках цифровизации отечественной медицины. Актуальные проблемы экономики и управления, (3), 35-39.
6. Сафуанов, Р. М., Лехмус, М. Ю., & Колганов, Е. А. (2019). Цифровизация системы образования. Вестник УГНТУ. Наука, образование, экономика. Серия: экономика, (2 (28)).